

CONSUMER DECISION PATTERN AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED LG OUTLETS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of consumer decision patterns on the organizational performance of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The inability of marketers and managers of LG outlets to properly understand their consumers' buying behavior seem to crumble and retard their profits, sales volume, and decrease their customer base in the Uyo metropolis. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in which primary data were obtained through questionnaire administration. The study population consisted of all the customers and staff of LG outlets located at Ikot Ekpene Road, Abak Road, Aka Road, and Oron Road within Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, a total sample size of 30 respondents was selected using the purposive sampling technique. The researchers employed both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the collected data. The Pearson correlation analysis technique was also employed to analyze the data. The reported p-values were used to test the significance of the stated research hypotheses. The finding was that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Another finding revealed a significant effect of consumer choice on sales volume. Further discovery was that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on profitability. It was concluded that consumer buying behavior has a significant effect on the organizational performance of selected LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Recommendations were that LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis should conduct market research to properly understand their consumers' buying behavior. The marketers of LG products should carefully explain products' features, quality, and durability to consumers in order for them to make their choices. There is a need for customer follow-up after sales to sustain such customers, which in turn will increase their customer base. Marketers at different LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis should embark on aggressive marketing strategies to boost their sales volume.

Keywords: Consumer Choice, Sales Volume, Customer Base, Profitabilit

Introduction

A consumer buys products and services for the motive of ultimate use or ownership. He has certain powers that accrue to him on the basis of who he is. These powers are legitimate power, rewards power, coercion, expert power, and reference power. It is assumed that fundamentally, in consumer buying behavior, consumers do not buy because of the product's function but as an offshoot of subjective perceived value. This does not diminish the function of the product but denotes the role that today's products play in exceeding their service limits. That fact notwithstanding, people determine their consumption patterns, and in trying to satisfy them, a lot of marketing is involved. This involves a level of creativity and the offer and exchange of value in an appealing way to persons, organizations, and groups. Consumers are concerned about their consumption patterns, and marketers take advantage of this to supply them with products of value. Marketers can have a better understanding of consumers' attitudes, their purchase motives, and frequency of purchase.

Consumer buying behavior is the buying behavior of final consumers, which comprise individuals or households, organizations, and governments who buy goods and services for personal consumption. Consumers make many buying decisions every day. Most LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis research consumer buying behavior and decisions to a great extent to determine what consumers buy, where they buy, how they buy, how much they buy, when they buy, and why they buy. Consumer buying behavior refers to all thoughts, feelings and actions that a consumer has or takes before or while buying any product, service or idea (Khaniwale, 2015). Consumer buying behavior includes all the decisions consumers make when spending their time and money. A consumer's buying behavior is influenced by personal factors such as choice, age, occupation, economic situation, lifestyle, consumer perceived value, family life cycle, perception, personality and self-concept (Zeithaml, 2000; Kotler and Armstrong, 2012; Perreault, 2014; Khan, 2016). In this study, consumer buying behavior is measured by consumer choice. Consumer choice is the consumer buying decision in selecting a particular product while foregoing alternative products.

Regarding organizational performance measurement, it is essential to pinpoint the primary objectives of an organization before identifying its performance indicators. Organizations launch their primary objectives based on their business vision or mission to suit the purpose for which they are created. From the viewpoint of Koko and Zuru (2019), once organizations have determined their specific objectives, they need to work on how best to achieve all of their objectives in a given period of time. Although the literature discloses that diverse organizations in dissimilar countries and industries tend to emphasize different performance measurement indicators, findings of past studies revealed that financial profitability and growth seemed to be the most common indicators for measuring organizational performance. However, from the viewpoint of Thomas and Kumara (2016), organizational performance should be measured by using not only financial but also non-financial or social measures. Organizations have different organizational objectives as compared to nonprofit ventures. Their organizational objectives are not only limited to financial profitability but also include sustainability. Hence, the need to measure organizational performance using both financial and non-financial performance indicators becomes imperative (Mustafa & Saat, 2013). In this study, the organizational performance indicators used are sales volume, customer base, and profitability. These are financial indicators with a blend of customer base as a non-financial indicator.

'Life is good(LG)' is an organization that deals with phones, electronic appliances, household appliances, and other related items. Their outlets are many in the Uyo metropolis. To establish the link between consumer buying

behavior and organizational performance, a study of this nature is imperative that seeks to examine the effect of consumer buying behavior on organizational performance of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Consumer choice or preference for the opportunity cost of LG products in the Uyo metropolis expands so much in time and sometimes with consumer clash of interests. The consumer wasted time in buying decisions by making choices and their willingness to part with their money is a big hindrance to sales volume, profitability, and customer base in general. The major decisions a buyer makes in a group and how his or her choice influences others are problems in buying behavior studies. Investigating how consumer buying behavior affects the volume of sales and profits as well as the customer base of LG products in the Uyo metropolis is still a major problem for LG marketers and managers in different outlets in Uyo. At the same time, lack of understanding the buying behavior of consumers and information devices by marketers and managers in reaching out to consumers at the right time and place to fasten purchase is an issue in determining consumers' choices. This inability of marketers and managers of LG outlets to properly study and understand their consumers' buying behavior has eroded and retarded their profits, sales volume, and decreased their customer base in the Uyo metropolis.

Study Objectives

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of consumer buying behavior on the organizational performance of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specific objectives were to;

- (i) Examine the effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- (ii) Establish the effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- (iii) Ascertain the effect of consumer choice on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Study Questions

- (i) What is the effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- (ii) What is the effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- (iii) What is the effect of consumer choice on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Study Hypotheses

In line with the problem statement and the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were expressed in null form:

Ho₁: There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization

Consumer Choice

Consumer choice is the ability of the consumer to select a particular product and forgo other products. Making a choice out of many alternatives is an important buying decision by consumers. The opportunity cost of buying selected products and foregoing others depends on consumer choice, which is influenced by consumer buying behavior. Barmola and Srivastava (2010) stated that consumer buying behavior focuses on the search, evaluation, purchase, consumption, and post purchase buying behavior of consumers, which includes the disposal of purchased products while keeping environmental and personal characteristics in mind. Also, Solomom (2011) postulated that consumer choice is related to the processes by which consumers select, purchase, use, or dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. Mukhtar (2013) added that consumer buying behavior and consumer choice cover a wide range of activities from the awareness of need stage through to post purchase buying behavior. Mfon, (2021) and Mfon & Uford (2023), assert that their study can provide a more thorough understanding of the choices consumers make when they decide to select a particular service marketer as opposed to the other, or even when they decide to continue the relationship with the marketer.

Consumer buying behavior focuses on activities that consumers engage in searching for, evaluating, selecting, buying, consuming, and disposing of products and/or services that are capable of satisfying their needs and desires, including other decision processes that precede and determine them (Nwulu & Ateke, 2014). Consumer buying behavior is a systematic process relating to buying decisions of consumers, which consist of activities such as identification of the problem, information search relating to the product, listing of alternative brands, evaluating the alternative (i.e., cost-benefit analysis), purchase decision, and post-purchase evaluation by marketers (Singh, 2016). Consumer buying behavior refers to the decision-making process of consumers who are directly involved in obtaining and using goods and services and how it leads to actual purchase, use and disposal of goods and services (Sunday & Bello, 2016). However, consumer preference to buy, use, and dispose of a product/service is mostly influenced by many factors of which consumer choice is central. This is because consumer choice is based on consumer experience, which is capable of building confidence that can sustain positive consumer buying behavior that supports their interest when buying goods and/or services.

Sales Volume

Is-haq (2019) stated that sales volume represents the size of business revenue generated by an enterprise/firm from sales over a period of time. Macaulay and Mfon (2023), define sales volume qualitatively as a record of the consistent increase in the order placed and the volume of products/services sold by the company through the use of social media. Sales volume could be stimulated by an increase in the prices of commodities and sales of more

commodities or goods (Mahmood, 2004). In another circumstance, it could be stimulated by both. However, sales volume that rises because of an increase in price could be linked to an adjustment in inflation and could therefore not be linked to actual or real growth in sales of products. However, if the costs remain at a low level, it could be described as a real increase in sales volume. On the other hand, an increase in sales of goods may imply growth in sales, which could be due to expansion in the geographical business environment, increase in the number of branches, and expansion of the quantity of products as well as the number of services provided.

Customer Base

Customer base describes the total number of customers patronizing an organization. Understanding the customer base will help an organization produce products that meet the demand of their customers. As a nonfinancial measurement of organizational performance, an increase in customer base may lead to improved organizational performance. An organization such as LG needs a strong customer base to survive in the long run. Hence, the need to measure the current and past customer bases in order to project future performance becomes imperative.

Profitability

Organizational performance is often hampered due to the non-availability of funds. Kosgei (2014) opines that production capacity and quality might be easily compromised if an organization experiences paucity or non-availability of funds. He believes that inadequate funds can lead to failure of an organization to meet its target growth in terms of quality standard products and demands of customers. Cho and Pucik (2005) believe that organizational superior financial performance is a way to satisfy investors and can be represented by profitability, growth, and market value. The sufficiency of funds practically determines the growth and quality of the products produced by an organization. Similarly, organizational growth is dependent on the availability and appropriate management of funds. According to Joseph and Yusuf (2021), profitability is the chief objective of every business undertaking, and profitability is the excess of income over expenditure. Income and expenses are the measurement indicators of profitability. Measuring profitability is paramount for the success and survival of any business. Nissim (2010) found a positive relationship between profitability, investment, and growth.

Theoretical Framework

Consumer Theory

Propounded by Martijn (2011), consumer theory is concerned with how a rational consumer makes consumption decisions. Consumer theory arises because the consumers' choice sets are assumed to be defined by certain prices and the consumers' income or wealth. There are certain assumptions in this theory. The assumption of perfect information is built deeply into the formulation of this choice problem, just as it is in the underlying choice theory (Blythe, 2005). Some alternative models treat the consumer as rational but uncertain about the products, for example, how a particular product will perform. Some products may be experience products, which the consumer can best learn about by trying the products. In this case, the consumer might want to buy some now and decide later whether to buy more. The relevance of this theory to the study hinges on the fact that the consumer's choice sets are manifest in their buying behavior.

Theory of Reasoned Action

The theory was propounded by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1980 (Nto, Aham & Kalu, 2018). The theory of reasoned action (TRA) is one of the three classic persuasion models of psychology and is also used in communication discourse as a theory of understanding persuasive messages. The theory of reasoned action was developed as an improvement over information integration theory. There are two important changes. First,

Reasoned Action adds another element to the process of persuasion, behavioral intention. That is, whenever our attitudes lead us to do one thing while the relevant norms suggest we should do something else, both factors influence our behavioral intent. For example, John's attitudes may encourage him to want to buy another brand of electronic appliances, but his friends may think other brands are not as high quality as the LG brand. Does John do what his attitude suggests (buy another brand of electronic appliances) or what the norms of his friends suggest (buy LG product)?

Specifically, Reasoned Action predicts that behavioral intent is created or caused by two factors: our attitudes and our subjective norms. This theory relates to the study in the sense that it helps marketers understand and predict the behavioral intents of consumers and how they process the marketing information and offers that are being sent to them.

Review of Empirical Studies

Ajibola (2012) studied the effect of consumer behavior and attitudinal tendencies toward purchase decisions of Unilever Nigeria Plc, Cadbury Nigeria Plc and United African Companies Plc. The researcher used tables and percentages for the presentation, scoring, and analysis of data. The hypotheses were tested using chi-square. It was found that the life cycle of a product influences purchase to a very great extent and that in some cases there is joint purchase decision in individuals and groups.

Akpoyomare, Adeosun, and Ganiyu (2012) examined the influence of product attributes on consumer purchase decisions in the Nigerian food and beverage industry. A descriptive research design was used to survey 400 customers of the two selected companies in the food and beverage industry. Data were collected through a questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficients were used for data analysis. The findings reveal a positive correlation between product attributes and consumer purchase decisions.

Mukhtar (2013) conducted a study on culture and values in consumer behavior in Nigerian experiences. A qualitative approach was used with 26 respondents drawn from across the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria and across different levels of educational attainment for data collection. The finding was that the major areas that affect buying behavior include the collectivist nature of most Nigerians and male dominance, which makes men the target for more highly involving goods than women. Further findings revealed that regional advertising is very attractive in the north because of the feeling of association with the product being advertised. Equally, religion plays a very delicate role because it defines what people find acceptable in terms of services or products.

Ndem and Ebitu (2019) conducted a comparative analysis of business and consumer buying behavior and decisions: opportunities and challenges in Nigeria. This study focused on traditional tools and methods used in product marketing. The major difference between the consumer and business markets was established. Organizations that sell to customers must do their best to understand customer buying behavior and the needs, resources, motivations, and buying processes that shape such buying behavior.

Chukwu, Musa, and Uzoma (2020) studied the influence of consumer value on consumer behavior toward made in Nigeria products in Rivers State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and the population consisted of all consumers of the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. A sample size of 335 consumers of manufactured products was selected using a convenient sampling technique. The hypothesis was tested using a multiple regression approach, and the findings revealed that consumers' value derived from products made in Nigeria has a significant influence on subsequent buying behavior. However, the influence was below average because they indicated their willingness to sometimes buy products made in Nigeria.

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Ulaikere, Asikhia, Adefulu and Ajike (2020) examined consumer shopping behavior effectors and service quality of selected online student-buyers in Lagos State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted. The population was 69,951 online student-buyers from selected private and public universities in Lagos State. A sample size of 1,177 was determined using the Cochran formula. Multistage sampling was adopted. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study findings revealed that consumer shopping behavior effectors had a significant effect on the service quality of online student-buyers in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted in which primary data were obtained through questionnaire administration. Chukwu, Musa, and Uzoma (2020) adopted this design and were able to achieve the study objectives because they successfully collected significant amount of data from a meaningful population size efficiently. The study population consisted of all the customers and staff of LG outlets located at Ikot Ekpene Road, Abak Road, Aka Road, and Oron Road within Uyo metropolis in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, a total sample size of 30 respondents was selected using the purposive sampling technique.

Data were collected through a questionnaire titled "Consumer Buying Behavior and Organizational Performance of Selected LG Outlets in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (CBBOPLGUMQ)". The questionnaire was carefully designed and administered to the respondents. The questionnaire contained sections A and B. Section A contains personal information about the respondents. Section B was the main body of the questionnaire that dealt with the study variables. This section contains close-ended statements using a four-point adjusted Likert scale instrument ranging from Strongly Agree (SA- 4points), Agree (A-3points), Strongly Disagree (SD-2points) and Disagree (D-1point).

The questionnaire was validated by marketing lecturers from Akwa Ibom State University and the University of Uyo. These experts assessed the relevance of each item in relation to the objectives of the study, the hypotheses to be tested, the language used in developing the items, and the comprehensibility of each item in relation to the cognitive level of the respondents. They validated the instrument by making necessary corrections, examining the contents, and ascertaining the clarification of ideas and the appropriateness of the items. The questionnaire was subjected to reliability of internal consistency using the Cronbach alpha test. The reliability index of 0.984 was obtained from the computation performed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

The researcher employed both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the collected data. Descriptive analysis was used to determine the mean, range of scores (minimum and maximum), standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for each variable of the study. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the strength and nature of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The reported p-values were used to test the significance of the stated research hypotheses. The variables used in this study were as follows:

Sales volume: a – proxy for organizational performance (dependent variable)

Customer base: a – proxy for organizational performance (dependent variable)

Profitability: a – proxy for organizational performance (dependent variable)

Consumer choice – proxy for consumer buying behavior (independent variable)

Data Presentation, Analysis, and Discussion of the Findings

The data gathered using the questionnaire are presented below:

Table 1: Number of questionnaires returned

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Returned	25	83.3
Not Returned	5	16.7
Total	30	100.0

Source: Field Survey Data (2023)

The above table portrays that out of 30 copies of the questionnaire administered, 25 copies were returned in a usable form, representing 83.3%, while 5 copies were not returned, representing only 16.7%. Therefore, the researchers used 25 copies of the returned questionnaire as the basis for the analysis.

Table 2: Gender distribution of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Male	15	60.0
Female	10	40.0
Total	25	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

Table 2 depicts the gender distribution of the respondents. From the table, out of 25 copies of questionnaire returned, 15 were males representing 60%, while 10 respondents were females representing 40%. This implies that most respondents were male.

Table 3: Age distribution of the respondents

Age range	Frequency	Percentage
Valid 25-30	6	24.0
31-35	10	40.0
36-40	5	20.0
41-above	4	16.0
Total	25	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

The table above shows that 6 respondents representing 24% of the sampled respondents are within the age bracket of 25-30 years, 10 respondents representing 40% are within the age bracket of 31–35 years, 5 respondents representing 20% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 36-40 years, and only 4 respondents 16% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 and above years.

Table 4: Marital status of the respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Single	8	32.0
Married	9	36.0
Divorced	5	20.0
Widowed	3	12.0

Total	25	100.0
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Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

The above table shows that 8 respondents were single, representing 32%, while 9 respondents were married, representing 36%. In addition, five respondents were divorced, representing 20% and another 3 respondents were widowed, representing 12%.

Table 5: Educational qualification distribution of the respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Valid SSCE	5	20.0
OND/NCE	7	28.0
HND/BSC	6	24.0
MBA/MSC	5	20.0
PHD	2	8.0
Total	25	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

The above table shows that out of 25 copies of the questionnaire correctly filled and returned, 5 respondents representing 20% were holders of SSCE, whereas 7 respondents representing 28% were holders of OND/NCE, 6 respondents representing 24% were holders of HND/B.Sc, 5 respondents representing 20% were MBA/M.Sc holders, and 2 respondents representing 8% were holders of P.hD educational qualifications.

Table 6: Working experience distribution of the respondents

Working Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Valid 0-5	11	44.0
6-10	5	20.0
11-16	6	24.0
17-above	3	12.0
Total	25	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

Table 6 shows that 11 respondents representing 44.4% have 0–5 years of working experience, 5 respondents representing 20% have 6–10 years of working experience. In addition, 6 respondents (24%) have years of working experience between 11 and 16 years and 3 respondents representing 12% have 17 years and above working experience.

Table 7: Rank distribution of the respondents

Rank	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Junior Staff	14	56.0
Senior Staff	6	24.0
Management Staff	5	20.0
Total	25	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS version 23 outputs

The above table depicts the rank distribution of respondents. The table revealed that 14 respondents representing 56% were junior staff, 6 respondents (24%) were senior staff, and 5 respondents representing 20% were management staff.

Research Question One

What is your experience with LG products as a consumer?

Table 8: Responses to the experience with LG products as a consumer

OPTIONS	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
I have purchased an LG TV in the last year	2	2	1	0	5(20%)
I have purchased an LG home theater in the last year	4	2	2	1	9(36%)
I have purchased an LG air conditioner in the last year	1	1	1	1	4(16%)
LG products are affordable	2	1	0	0	3(12%)
LG products are standard	2	1	1	0	4(16%)
Total	11(44%)	7(28%)	5(20%)	2(8%)	25(100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 8 shows that out of 25 respondents, 11 respondents representing 44% strongly agreed that there is a relationship between consumer buying behavior and their experience with LG products, whereas 7 respondents representing 28% agreed to the claim. In addition, five respondents representing 20% strongly disagreed with the claim while only 2 respondents representing 8% disagreed. We conclude that there is a relationship between consumer buying behavior and their experience with LG products.

Research Question Two

What are the sales volume ranges per week as an employee?

Table 9: Responses on sales volume ranges per week as an employee

Sales volume ranges per week (₦)	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
100,000 – 999,000	6	2	0	0	8(32%)
1,000,000 – 9,000,000	3	3	0	0	6(24%)
10,000,000 – 40,000,000	1	0	1	1	3 (12%)
41,000,000 – 70,000,000	1	0	1	1	3 (12%)
71,000,000 – 100,000,000	1	1	0	0	2 (8%)
Above 100,000,000	1	1	0	1	3 (12%)
Total	13(52%)	7(28%)	2(8%)	3(12%)	25(100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 9 shows that out of 25 respondents, 13 respondents representing 52% strongly agreed that the sales volume per week is encouraging, whereas 7 respondents representing 28% agreed to the claim. The analysis further shows

that 2 respondents representing 8% strongly disagreed with the claim while 3 respondents representing 12% disagreed.

Research Question Three

What do you think is your customer base per week?

Table 10: Responses on customer base per week

Customer base per week	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
10-29	5	2	2	1	10 (40%)
30-49	3	3	3	0	9 (36%)
50-69	1	1	0	0	2 (8%)
70 -89	1	0	0	1	2 (8%)
90 -100	1	0	1	0	2 (8%)
Total	11 (44%)	6 (24%)	6 (24%)	2 (8%)	25 (100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 10 reveals that 11 respondents representing 44% strongly agreed that they have a good customer base per week, whereas 6 respondents representing 24% agreed to the claim. However, 6 respondents representing 24% strongly disagreed with the claim, while only 2 respondents representing 8% disagreed.

Research Question Four

What is the range of profit your outlet makes monthly?

Table 11: Responses on the range of monthly profit

Range of monthly profit	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
100,000 – 999,000	2	1	1	1	5 (20%)
1,000,000 -5,000,000	3	3	2	0	8 (32%)
6,000,000 – 10,000,000	3	4	3	1	11 (44%)
11,000,000 -15,000,000	1	0	0	0	1 (4%)
16,000,000 -20,000,000	0	0	0	0	0 (0%)
21,000,000 and above	0	0	0	0	0 (0%)
Total	9 (36%)	8 (32%)	6 (24%)	2 (8%)	25 (100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 11 reveals that 9 respondents representing 36% strongly agreed that they make reasonable monthly profits, whereas 8 respondents representing 32% agreed to the claim. However, 6 respondents representing 24% strongly disagreed with the claim, while only 2 respondents representing 8% disagreed.

Research question five

What is the effect of consumer buying behavior on the organizational performance of LG outlets in the Uyo

metropolis?

Table 12: Responses on the effect of consumer buying behavior on organizational performance of LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis

OPTIONS	SA	A	SD	D	TOTAL
Our customers' choice of LG products boosts our sales volume	3	2	1	3	9 (36%)
We have a large customer base because more customers come for our products.	2	1	2	1	6 (24%)
We make more profits because our customers choose to purchase our products.	5	0	3	2	10 (40%)
Total	10 (40%)	3 (12%)	6 (24%)	6 (24%)	25 (100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 12 shows that 10 respondents representing 40% strongly agreed that consumer buying behavior has an effect on the organizational performance of LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis, while 3 respondents (12%) agreed to the claim. Also, 6 respondents (24%) strongly disagreed with the claim while 6 respondents (24%) disagreed. It could be deduced from the respondents' opinion that the research construct and items are sufficient to guarantee scientific analysis and a valid conclusion. Obliquely, this could be interpreted to mean that each independent research construct or variable has some kind of effect on the dependent research construct or variable when

Table 13 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
sales volume	25	1	4	2.89	1.040
customer base	25	1	4	2.86	1.122
profitability	25	1	4	3.08	.982
consumer choice	25	1	4	2.83	1.171
Valid N (listwise)	25				

statistically and scientifically tested.

Descriptive Statistics Results

Source: SPSS outputs computed by the researcher

Table 13 displays that the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria has a mean score of 2.89 with a standard deviation of 1.040, indicating that the deviation from the mean is low ; hence, the data are clustered around the mean. The minimum value of sales volume was 1.0, and a maximum value of 4.0 was recorded. These statistics reveal that the level of deviation of the minimum from the maximum value is low. Thus, indicating a low disparity in the level of sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The mean value for customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria is 2.86 with a standard deviation of 1.122. The minimum value is one and the maximum value is 4. The statistics reveal that the level of deviation of the minimum from the maximum value is low. Thus, indicating a low disparity in the customer base. Profitability maintained a mean value of 3.08, and the standard deviation was 0.982, which implies high variations in profitability. The maximum and minimum values were 1 and 4 percent, respectively. From the descriptive statistics results, it was further revealed that consumer choice showed low disparity in the level of consumer choice, as evidenced by the mean scores and standard deviation of 2.83 and 1.171, respectively.

Test of the Research Hypotheses

The first hypothesis was that “There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria”.

Table 14: Correlation Results for Hypothesis One

Variables		sales volume	consumer choice
sales volume	Pearson Correlation	1	.720*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.009
	N	25	25
consumer choice	Pearson Correlation	.720*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	
	N	25	25

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS outputs computed by the researcher

In Table 14, the correlation coefficient analysis obtained was 0.720, which indicates that consumer choice has a significant effect on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample represented by N used for the analysis was 25, and the level of significance of the study or otherwise known as the p-value of the study was 0.009, which is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Hence, the outcome of the analysis affirms a positive correlation between the dependent and independent variables. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted, which states that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The second hypothesis was that “There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria”.

Table 15: Correlation Results for Hypothesis Two

Variables		customer base	consumer choice
customer base	Pearson Correlation	1	.615*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
	N	25	25
consumer choice	Pearson Correlation	.615*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
	N	25	25

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS outputs computed by the researcher

In Table 15, the correlation coefficient analysis obtained was 0.615, which indicates that consumer choice has a significant effect on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample represented by N used for the analysis was 25, and the level of significance of the study or otherwise known as the p-value of the study was 0.010, which is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Hence, the outcome of the analysis affirms a positive correlation between the dependent and independent variables. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted, which states that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The third hypothesis was that “There is no significant effect of consumer choice on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria”.

Table 16: Correlation Results for Hypothesis Three

		profitability	consumer choice
profitability	Pearson Correlation	1	.867*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	25	25
consumer choice	Pearson Correlation	.867*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	25	25

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS outputs computed by the researcher

In Table 16, the correlation coefficient analysis obtained was 0.867, which indicates that consumer choice has a significant effect on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample represented by N used for the analysis was 25, and the level of significance of the study or otherwise known as the p-value of the study was 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Hence, the outcome of the analysis affirms a positive correlation between the dependent and independent variables. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was accepted, which states that there

is a significant effect of consumer choice on the profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

In the first hypothesis, a Pearson correlation r-value of 0.720 indicates a positive effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, because the correlation coefficient of 0.720 was over 0.50, it implies that there is a strong and positive correlation between consumer choice and sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Because the p value of 0.009 was less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the finding was that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on the sales volume of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

In the second hypothesis, a Pearson correlation r-value of 0.615 indicates a positive effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, since the correlation coefficient of 0.615 was over 0.50, it denotes that there is a strong and positive correlation between consumer choice and customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Since the p value of 0.010 was less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the finding was that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on the customer base of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Furthermore, a Pearson correlation r-value of 0.867 in the third hypothesis indicates a positive effect of consumer choice on profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, since the correlation coefficient of 0.867 was over 0.50, it denotes that there is a strong and positive correlation between consumer choice and profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Because the p value of 0.000 was less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the finding was that there is a significant effect of consumer choice on profitability of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of consumer buying behavior on the organizational performance of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Consumer choice, which measured consumer buying behavior, affected all the dependent variables that captured organizational performance. Significantly, the results of the nature of effect on variables were positive. Based on the study findings, it is concluded that consumer buying behavior has a significant effect on the organizational performance of selected LG outlets in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The researchers make some policy recommendations that LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis should conduct market research to properly understand their consumers' buying behavior. The marketers of LG products should carefully explain the products' features, quality, and durability to consumers in order for them to make their choices. There is a need for customer follow-up after sales to sustain such customers, which in turn will increase their customer base. Marketers at different LG outlets in the Uyo metropolis should embark on aggressive marketing strategies to boost their sales volume. Employing different marketing communication strategies will attract more potential and existing consumers and stimulate their profitability.

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